

ASSESSMENT OF FACTORS AFFECTING GARRI MARKETING IN SELECTED TWO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREAS OF OGUN STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study was conducted to ascertain factors affecting Garri marketing in Ijebu East and Ijebu-North Local Government Area Ogun State, Nigeria. A multi-stage sampling technique was used to select the sample size of 120 respondents using structured questionnaire to generate the required information from the respondents. Data analysis was carried out using descriptive and inferential statistics such as frequency table, percentage, mean and standard deviation was used to described socio-economic characteristics of the respondents (garri marketers), while budgetary analysis was used to estimate profitability level of garri Marketers. Ordinary Least Square was used to identify factors affecting garri marketing respectively. The result revealed that Garri marketing business is common among women and 98.3% of the respondents had formal education. Females dominated the business while males are very few. The budgetary analysis result revealed that garri marketing was found to be highly profitable at net profit of ₦33,356.7531 and gross margin ₦34,827.8839per annum. The Total revenue for garri marketing took ₦401,113.0003..The study revealed that marketing of Garri is a profitable business in the selected Local Government areas of Ogun State. Government should endeavor to help garri marketers by making loans with low or no interest rates and make sure that disbursing partners adhere to official regulations interest rate and load requirement. Socio-economic characteristics determinants which have direct link with enhanced family life and improve standard of living should be addressed properly.

Keywords: *Profitability, Garri Marketing, Garri Marketers, Budgetary Analysis.*

Introduction

Garri is a versatile cassava product, Garri can utilized in a variety of ways, it can be soaked in cold water and consumed directly with some light accompaniment such as sweetness, fish and groundnut. Garri can be eaten dry or soaked in water as Eba and consumed with soups and stews. The approximate and physical properties of Garri is a function of the cassava variety, age of cassava, time of harvesting, processing method, packaging method, storage conditional and duration of storage

(Oduro *et al*, 2010). Garri is a convenient food with short preparation time especially for commercial demand, its cheapness, ease of storage and preparation for consumption. Garri is a major staple food in Nigeria. Private and public investments are required to reach this vision (Plucknett, Truman & Robert,2000). A staple food, as defined by IITA, (2007) is one that is eaten regularly and which provide a large proportion of the population's energy and/or nutrients. Garri which is a by-product of Cassava reach in carbohydrate, mainly starch and is a major source of energy. With the exception of sugar cane, Garri is the highest source of carbohydrate. It is consumed by several millions of people in the African continent, especially in the West Africa sub region (Ogiehor, 2022).

As cash crops, cassava generates cash income for the largest number of households in comparison with other staples (Nweke 1994). A large proportion of total production, probably larger than that of most staples, is planted annually for sale. Garri is an essential part of the diet of 500 million people and provides a livelihood for millions of farmers, processors and traders (IITA, 2013). Garri is a granular food product produced by grating cassava roots into a mash, fermenting and dewatering the mash into a wet cake, and roasting the wet material into gelatinized particles. Garri has a slightly sour taste and it could be white or cream depending on the variety of cassava used and the processing method adopted. Africa is one of the continents of the world where some 600 million people are dependent on cassava for food (International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD, 2013). Garri is the most popular form in which cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) is consumed by several millions of people in the African continent, especially in the West Africa sub region (Ogiehor, 2022; Okonkwo, &Ugwa, 2015). The various forms of consumptions as snack (refreshing light meal when soaked in cold water and eaten with coconut, banana, smoked fish or peanut) and as major meal (when made into thick paste called “eba” and eaten with various types of African soups) make it the most popular diet amongst the rich and the poor, with acceptability cutting across the various socio-economic and multi-ethnic groups in Africa (Ogiehor & Ikenebomeh, 2014).

Problem Statement

Despite Nigeria's position as the major producer of garri in the world, the level of income that accrues to garri producers and processors after huge investments of capital and labour is a pittance. The Garri market is not diversified, the products are not diversified lack of supply of raw materials, competition from alternative product to the by-product of garri, government agricultural climate change policy and the challenges e.g high production cost of garri production from price fluntuations and limited

resources of supply, there is little or no product quality control or standard to ensure constituency, poor and inadequate infrastructural facilities, good roads and regular water supplies are needed, these are, vital to value addition ; hence, famers will have low income, because most of farmers and industrialist find it impossible to obtain loans from bank, method of processing is traditional by using small and inefficient equipment and manual labour. This makes the processing labour-intensive and labour productivity is low (Nestle & Fresco, 1993).

The field labour requirement contrasts with the high demand of labour for garri processing. Thus, any cost-saving or yield-increasing technology may not fully translate into expanded production if there is no matching cost-saving technology for garri processing, hence, the packing is very important to earn substantive income. Sorting and packaging activities are not carried out further reducing the ability of using a sound marketing system to boost farmers' income and ensure adequate protection of consumers.

Among other constraints, the poor condition of the Nigerian rural roads contributes to high deterioration of fresh cassava and makes transportation of processed products to market very difficult. More so, some products are contaminated with undesirable organisms due to the drudgery associated with the traditional processing and therefore reduce the market quality. Improved cassava processing and utilization techniques would greatly increase labour efficiency, productivity, income, raise marketing opportunities and upgrade the nutrition and living standard of the cassava farmers and processors. Inefficient and inadequate storage system is another constraints associated with the poor marketing for agricultural produce in Nigeria. As a consequence there is a substantial waste at the farm level and the poor storage system also contribute to price fluctuation in the agricultural market whereby produce prices are low during harvest time's adversely affecting farmers' incomes. Standardized system of grading and measurement, which enhances marketing efficiency, is not a feature of agricultural market in Nigeria. Grades are determined arbitrarily by sizes, colour or smell. Measures come in various types of metal and plastic bowls, tins, baskets e.t.c. Most of the measure is susceptible to manipulate to Change volume in an attempt to take the advantage of buyers.

This is why it vary within markets, across markets and from time in the market place. Since production is not complete until the product get to the hands of the final consumers and Garri market has been very unstable with its prices experiencing volatile swings in both price and availability.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study is to investigate the factors affecting Garri marketing in selected two (2) Local Government Areas of Ogun state.

The specific objectives are to:

- i. describe the socioeconomic characteristics of Garri marketer,
- ii. determine the various factors affecting Garri marketing
- iii. examine the profitability of Garri marketer.

Conceptual Theory

Managerial Efficiency Theory of Profits

This theory recognizes that some firms are more efficient than others in terms of management of productive operations and successfully meeting the needs of consumers. Firms with average level of efficiency earn average rate of return. Firms with higher managerial skills and production efficiency are required to be compensated by above-normal profits (i.e. economic profits). Therefore, this theory is also called compensatory theory of profits. Frank Knight argued that economic profit is a return to the entrepreneur in exchange of the risk undertaken by him (her) in the operation of a business enterprise. Because the other three factors of production (land, labour and capital) have contractual agreements of payment for their services – wages, rent and interest, economic profit is a residue that may exist after these other factors have been compensated. No other factor income can be zero or negative' but profit can be, since at times there may be no profit at all or even a loss. The compensatory theory of profits focuses on "the notion that above-normal rates of return (or economic profits) are the result of the ability of certain firms and entrepreneurs to outperform their competitors. This superior performance may stem from the fact that they are better able to satisfy current consumer demands or predict future demands." High profits are the signal that consumers want more of the output of the industry, high profits provide the incentive for firms to expand output and for more firms to enter the industry in the long run. For a firm of above average efficiency, profits represent the reward for greater efficiency. On the other hand, lower profits or losses are the signal that consumers want less of the commodity and that production methods may not be efficient. It is often argued that profit arises as a result of managerial efficiency. It can be shown in many instances that management, through more efficient operations, can reduce the cost of doing business, anticipate and offset changes

that will adversely affect the company's income, adopt new marketing techniques, improve product quality and expand the product line in order to increase profit.

Empirical Review

Off season production can take advantage of higher prices. Producers can benefit the most if they can manage to offset the costs or expenses incurred, which are usually higher than the ones generally incurred during the regular season, with higher sales prices (Shepherd & Ilboudo, 2010; Okafor & Okonkwo, 2022). Thus counter-seasonal production can mitigate the effects of the decline in prices observed at harvest time (Shepherd & Ilboudo, 2010; Sani *et al.*, 2011; Okonkwo & Ugwa 2020). Market information service (MISs) can also help improve producer's income. To be useful market information services (MISs) must provide information on prices in the short term and on the places and markets where it is more convenient to sell (Shepherd & Ilboudo, 2010; Otaokpukpu, et. al. 2017). They must also show the trends of seasonal and inter-annual price variations. This according to Shepherd and Ilboudo (2010) allows producers to decide whether to stockpile or sell and to know whether to sell all their products or to keep some for their own use or for future sale.

Methodology

The research work employed a survey design. A total of population of 172 members of garri marketers were studied.

Methods of Data Collection

Both primary and secondary data were used for this study. Primary data was gathered using questionnaire that was personally administered and interviews conducted on Garri marketers

Sampling Techniques and Sample size

A multi-stage sampling technique was employed to select respondents. In the first stage, one zone was picked out of 4 zones in Ogun-State (OGADEF, 2010). In the second stage two (2) Local Government Areas were selected from the zone: Ijebu-North and Ijebu-East Local Government Areas. In the third stage, three (3) communities / towns were randomly selected from the chosen Local Government Areas (Ijebu-Igbo, Ago-iwoye, Oru/Ilaporu-Ijebu, Ijebu-Ode, Ijebu-Mushin and Ilese-Ijebu) respectively the towns/ communities were selected because of their high concentration of Garri marketing in those towns. In the last stage twenty (20) Garri marketers were randomly selected from each towns making a total of 120 respondents.

Methods of Data Analysis

The study data used both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics such as; frequency table, percentage, mean and standard deviation, and inferential such as Budgetary analysis and Ordinary Least Square (OLS).

Socio Economic Characteristics of Garri Marketers

Descriptive analysis was used to describe socio-economic characteristics of garri marketers in the study area.

Factors Affecting Garri Marketing

Ordinary least square (OLS) was used to determine the various factors affecting Garri marketing. The regression model is specified as:

$$Y = f(X_1, X_2, \dots, X_{13})$$

Where;

Y_1 = Net income (N).

X_1, X_2, \dots, X_{12} are independent variables.

X_1 = Bad road

X_2 = High cost of transportation (N)

X_3 = Poor and instable price of Garri

X_4 = High purchase of cassava tuber (N)

X_5 = Lack of capital (N)

X_6 = Poor sales

X_7 = Poor storage facility

X_8 = Competitiveness

X_9 = Risk of accident and robbery

X_{10} = Credit sales

X_{11} = Shortage of labour

X_{12} = High labour cost

β_0 = Constant or intercept.

Profitability of Garri Marketing

Budgetary analysis was used to determine the profitability level of Garri marketers in the study area which is stated as follows:

Gross Margin (GM) estimation: This is the difference between the total revenue and total variable cost. It is expressed mathematically thus,

$$GM = TR - TVC \dots \dots \dots (1)equ$$

A positive *GM* indicates that the operating cost is being covered and the business can be sustained.

Where:

GM = Gross Margin

TR = Total Revenue

TVC = Total Variable Cost

$$TR = P \times Q \dots \dots \dots (2)equ$$

Where,

P = Price of garri sold per plastic (₦/Kg)

Q = Quantity of garri purchased per annum (Kg)

Net Income or Net Margin (π) Analysis

This is the difference between the total revenue (*TR*) and total cost (*TC*). Mathematically,

$$NI = TR - TC \dots \dots \dots (3)equ$$

Where,

NI = Net Income or Profit (₦)

TR = Total Revenue

TC = Total Cost

$$PI = NI/TR \dots \dots \dots (4)equ$$

$$RRI = NI/TC \times 100/I \dots \dots \dots (5)equ$$

$$RRVC (\%) = TR - TFC/TVC \times 100/I \dots \dots \dots (6)equ$$

$$OR = TVC/TR \dots \dots \dots (7)equ$$

Where,

PI = Profitability Index

RRI = Rate of Return on Investment

RRVC= Rate of Return on Variable Cost

OR= Operating Ratio.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1: Distribution of Socio-economics Characteristics of the Respondents.

Age	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative
≤ 30	12	10.0	10.0
31 – 40	50	41.7	51.7.
41 – 50	42	35.0	86.7
51 – 60	16	13.3	100.0
Total	120	100.0	
Mean	Std. Dev.		
40.8	8.25		
Gender			
Male	11	8.2	8.2
Female	110	91.8	100.0
Total	120	100.0	
Mean	Std. Dev.		
1.88	0.3		
Marital status			
Single	3	2.5	2.5
Married	99	82.5	85
Divorced	7	5.8	90.8
Widowed	10	8.3	99.2
Separated	1	0.8	100
Total	120	100.0	
Mean	Std. Dev.		
2.25	0.66		
Educational level			
Noformal education	2	1.7	1.7
Primary	33	27.5	29.2
Secondary	64	53.3	82.5
Tertiary	21	17.5	100.0
Total	120	100.0	
Mean	Std. Dev.		
10.69	3.53		
Religion			
Christianity	89	74.2	74.2
Islam	29	24.2	98.4
Traditional worshipper	2	1.6	100
Total	120	100.0	
Mean	Std. Dev.		
1.39	0.61		
Major occupation			
Farming	60	50.0	50.0

Garri marketer	29	24.2	74.2
Trading	10	8.3	82.5
Artisan	15	12.5	95.0
Others	6	5.0	100
Total	120	100.0	
Mean	Std. Dev.		
2.97	1.7		
Years of experience			
Less than equal 3	5	4.2	4.2
4 – 6	26	21.7	25.8
7 – 9	19	15.8	41.7
10 – 12	30	25.0	66.7
13 and above	40	33.3	100
Total	120	100.0	
Mean	Std. Dev.		
3.58	1.24		
Household size			
Less than equal 3	9	7.5	7.5
4 – 6	84	70.0	77.5
7– 9	21	17.5	95.0
10 – 12	5	4.2	99.2
13 and above	1	0.8	100
Total	120	100.0	
Sources of finance			
Cooperative	36	30.0	30.0
Friend and relative	13	10.8	40.8
Micro finance bank	11	9.2	50.0
Personal savings	60	50.0	100
Total	120	100.0	
Mean	Std. Dev.		
4.32	2.09		

Source: Field Survey Data, 2023

From the Table 1, it was revealed that substantial percentage (41.7%) and (35.0%) of the respondents had their age fell within 31 – 40 years and 41-50 age bracket, which also shown the majority of them were in their productive age they had enough strength and agility to work very hard. Also, 13.3% and 10.0% of the respondent had their age fell within 51 – 60 and below 31 years respectively. This implies that the respondents are in their prime working age. Gender of the respondents was analyzed and the results showed that majority (91.8%) of the respondents were female while 8.2% of the

respondents were male this indicated that females contribute significantly to Garri marketing in the study area than males counterpart. The marital status of the respondents shows that 82.5% of the respondents were married, 2.5% were single, 5.8% were divorced, 8.3% were widowed and 0.8% were separated. This showed that highest percentage of the sampled respondents were married and they had family responsibilities. The study revealed that 33% of the cassava marketers had primary school education only, 64% also were secondary school leavers, 21% had educated up to tertiary institution level while 1.7% of the respondents had no formal education. The result showed that majority of the respondents are educated and they can write and read. The study revealed that majority 74.2% of the cassava marketers practiced Christianity as religion while 24.2% of the sampled Garri marketer practiced Islam and 0.6% practiced traditional. The respondents are associated with one religion or the other, which implies that there is no religious discrimination in their involvement in Garri marketing. The study revealed that majority 50.0% of the respondents predominantly engage in farming as their major occupation while 24.2% of the respondents were involved in Garri marketing only and 8.3% engaged in trading other business. The Garri marketers whose major occupations are neither engaged in farming, nor trading, nor Garri marketing while other jobs involved by some respondents include artisan 12.5% and 5.0% who engages in some other activities respectively. This showed that majority of them engaged in other activities besides Garri marketing to increase their income. The study revealed that 21.7% of the sampled Garri marketers had between 4-6 years of experience in Garri marketing, 15.8% had between 7-9 years of experience, 25.0% had between 10-12 years of experience, while 33.3% had 13 and above years of cassava marketing experience and 4.2% had less than or 3 years of experience. This implied that larger percentage of them (74.1%) had experience between 7 and 13 years and above in Garri marketing which showed that Garri marketers in the study area were not new in their businesses.

The Majority (70.0%) of the respondents had between 4-6 persons as household size while 17.5%, 4.2% and 0.8% of the respondents had between 7-9, 10-12 and, 13 and above persons as household size respectively. 7.5% of the respondents also had 3 persons or less than as their household's size. This revealed that respondents had considerably moderate household size in the study area. The majority of the respondent (50.0%) used their personal savings in starting and maintaining the business (10.8%) sourced their finance from friends and relatives while (30.0%) obtained credit from cooperatives, (9.2%) obtained credit from micro finance bank.

Table 2: Distribution of Profitability of Garri Marketing in the Study Area

Description	(₦)	% of Total Cost
Revenue (₦)		
Value of Garri Sold (₦)	39507.9670	98.49
Value of Garriflakes sold (₦)	605.0333	1.51
Total Revenue(₦)	40113.0003	100
Variable Cost Items:		
Labour Cost (₦)	4233.7331	62.66
Transportation Cost (₦)	601.2500	8.89
Nylon Cost (₦)	450.1333	6.67
Total Variable Cost ₦	5285.1164	78.22
Gross Margin (₦)	34827.8839	
Fixed Cost Items:		
Interest on Loan (₦)	487.5001	7.22
Sieve (₦)	207.0833	3.07
Sack (₦)	260.6111	3.86
Bowl (₦)	128.0931	1.90
Drum (₦)	386.8432	5.73
Total Fixed Cost (₦)	1470.1308	21.78
Total Cost	6756.2472	100
Net Income	33356.7531	
Profitability Indices:		
Profitability Index or Returns on Sale	0.83	
Rate of Return on Variable Cost (%)	293.71%	
Operating Ratio	0.13	

Source: Field Survey Data, 2020

Description of Cost and Returns Structure of Garri Processing in the Study Area.

Budgetary result from garri marketing in the study area was analyzed and presented using their mean values. The total revenue from the business was estimated at ₦40113.0003. The total variable cost was estimated at ₦5,285.1164 and accounted for 78.22 % while fixed cost was estimated at ₦1,470.1308 at 21.78% and total cost was estimated the be ₦6756.2472. This showed that variable cost constituted the larger proportion of cost of Garri marketing business for the respondents. In addition, Total Revenue (TR) and Gross Margin (GM) of the business were estimated at ₦401,113.0003 and ₦3,4827,8839 respectively. The result showed that Profitability Index or Returns on Sale (PI or RS), Rate of Return on Variable Cost (RRVC) and Operating Ratio (OR) were 0.83, 293.71% and 0.13%. The implication of this is that Garri marketers made profit in their business and which invariable increased their returns on investment and implied that Garri marketing is profitable and viable in the study area. Also, it was revealed that for every one naira spent on Garri marketing there was a return of ₦80.21

Table 3: Factors Affecting Garri Marketing in the Study Area

Variables	OLS	SEMI-LOG	EXPONENTIAL	DOUBLE-LOG
Bad Road (X ₁)	-0.054 (-0.337)	-0.055 (-0.445)	-0.040 (-0.092)	-0.005 (-0.022)
High cost of transportation	-0.350*** (-3.436)	-0.334** (-2.168)	-0.369** (-2.472)	-0.292* (-1.656)

(X ₂)				
Poor and price instability of product (X ₃)	0.121 (1.216)	0.209 (1.264)	0.231* (1.861)	0.230 (0.886)
High cost of labour (X ₄)	-0.240 (-1.362)	-0.164 (-1.339)	-0.335* (-1.734)	-0.175 (-1.004)
Lack of capital (X ₅)	-0.106 (-0.481)	-0.177 (-1.087)	0.072 (-0.862)	-0.106 (-0.527)
Competitiveness (X ₆)	0.007(0.025)	-0.008 (-0.048)	0.109 (0.070)	0.051 (0.224)
Poor storage facilities (X ₇)	0.073 (0.546)	0.158 (0.818)	0.216 (0.860)	0.129 (0.479)
Poor sales (X ₈)	0.054 (0.664)	0.009 (0.059)	0.249** (2.352)	0.139 (0.778)
Risk of accident and robbery (X ₉)	0.039 (0.188)	-0.074 (-0.515)	0.075 (0.682)	0.007 (0.039)
Credit sales (X ₁₀)	-0.019 (-1.201)	-0.218 (-0.803)	-0.113 (-1.010)	-0.116 (-0.605)
Shortage of labour (X ₁₁)	0.621** (2.378)	0.264* (1.623)	0.132 (0.981)	0.201 (0.925)

Model Fit Test

Constant	199968.374** (2.509)	181924.310** (2.102)	10.184*** (7.424)	10.979*** (6.579)
R	0.446 ^a	0.536 ^a	0.744 ^a	0.654 ^a
R ²	0.199	0.204	0.471	0.027
Adjusted R ²	0.102	0.035	0.056	-0.689
R ² change	0.109	0.204	0.206	0.301
F change	2.329**	1.142	1.999*	1.286
Df1	13	13	13	13
Df2	104	68	109	59

Source: Field Survey Data, 2023 ***, **, *, significant at 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance respectively

Description of Factors Affecting Garri Marketing in the Study Area

Based on the R², F-value, t-statistic and theoretical expectation of the variables, exponential function was chosen as lead equation. Table 3 showed the regression estimates for the factors affecting profitability of the garri marketing enterprise in Ogun State. Table 3: revealed that R was 74.4% and R² was 47.1% of Garri marketers respectively was explained by the independent variables included in the model. The F- statistics (1.999) confirms the suitability of the overall regression equation. The

results revealed that four of the eleven variables included in the model were significantly affecting profitability of the Garri marketing enterprise in the study area. The high cost of transportation was significant at 5% level and negatively correlated profitability of Garri marketers. The result was a prior expectation because as the cost of transportation increases, it will affect price of the product thus, will reduce profitability. Poor and price instability of product was significant at 10% level and positively significant to factors affecting profitability of Garri marketing. This implied that a unit increase in poor and price instability of product while every other things remaining constant, will have no effect on the profitability of Garri marketing. High cost of labour had negative effect at 10% significant relationship with the product. This was expected because a priori expectation showed that high cost of labour will invariably affect price of Garri, thus reduce profitability of the marketers. The poor sales had a significant positive effect at 5% significant level on Garri profitability marketing in the study area. This implied that poor sales is more likely to affect profitability of Garri marketers. The possible reason for this result could be that most respondents reduce price to get more customers and get higher return on scale. While the rest variables Bad road, lack of capital, competitiveness, poor storage facilities, risk of accident and robbery, credit sales and shortage of labour were not significance.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of the Major Findings

Socio-economic characteristics of garri marketers include; age, gender, marital status, educational level, religion, major occupation, other occupation, years of experience etc were analyzed and revealed how they can bring alterations in profitability of garri marketing. Analysis of age of respondents showed that majority (41.7%) of Garri marketers were between the bracket age of 31-40 years. 90.8% of the respondents were reported to be females and 82.5% of the total sampled garri marketers were married. Majority of the respondents (53.3%) had secondary school certificate. Analytical results from the study also revealed that Christians were the majority 74.2% among garri marketers of the sampled respondents. Farmers was revealed to be the most participants in Garri marketing occupation of Garri marketing Farming among the total sampled respondents happened to be 50.0% as major job while other occupations took 50.0% as main job ranged from artisan, trading and others and 33.3% of the respondents had 13 years and above experience in garri marketing. Results of the analysis of household size of garri marketers in the study area confirmed that 70% of the total sampled respondents had between 4-6 household members. Among the respondents. Personal savings (50%) was source of the finance mostly used among the marketers in the study area. The

profitability of garri marketers were analyzed using budgetary analysis. The mean Total Cost (TC) was ₦6,756.2472 with the Total Fixed Cost (TFC) as ₦1,470.1308. The Total Cost (TVC) was calculated as ₦5285,1164.. TVC had a percentage value of 72.22% and TFC had a percentage of 21.78%. Operating ratio for Garri marketing in the study was 0.13. The figure signifies profitability in the business. 0.83 on rate of return reveals that for every one naira spent on garri marketing there was a return of N80.30 on the investment. The results signified that garri marketing is a profitable business.

Conclusion

As gari marketers had much experienced years in their business, the experience help them to be more efficient in their business in the study area. Majority of the respondents were females, with an average age of 31-40 years, it shown that females were more than males in this enterprise. Majority had married, and they had family members to cater for. Most of them had one form of formal education which revealed that they can write and read. Garri marketers had moderate household size in the study area. Lastly, Garri marketing is highly viable and profitable venture in the study area.

Recommendations

In line with the overview of this research work, recommendations proffered to better the plight of garri producers in the study area are:

1. Socio-economics characteristics determinants which have direct link with enhanced family life, and improve standard of living should be addressed properly.
2. Persons who were of younger age especially singles who are still very active and agile to work should be encouraged to go into garri processing enterprise and marketing based on the fact that the business is profitable. This will serves as a source of employment for those who are jobless. This will keep them busy rather than wandering and becoming nuisance to the society.
3. Government should assist or help garri marketers to have access to loans with no or low interest rates and make sure that disbursing partners adhere to official regulations interest rate and loan requirements.

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